

IMBALANCE OF IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN CHRONIC VIRAL HEPATITIS

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For many countries, the situation with acute infections caused by viral hepatitis remains unresolved: tens of thousands of cases and hundreds of deaths are registered annually, most of them in vulnerable age groups (the elderly and children under the age of 1 year) and almost exclusively in low- and middle-income countries [1,2].

The purpose of the study: to develop a method for diagnosing and predicting complications of chronic viral hepatitis, taking into account the immune status.

Materials and methods: A total of 64 patients were included in the study, of which 30 patients (group 1) aged 38 to 79 years with chronic viral hepatitis C (HCV) and 34 patients (group 2) aged 31 to 67 years with chronic viral hepatitis B (HCV). At the same time, the average age of patients was y patients of group 1 54.6 ± 1.89 years, y patients of group 2 45.4 ± 1.44 years. The control group consisted of 32 healthy people aged 35 to 54 years (average age 44.3 ± 0.95).

Results and discussion. The immunological parameters of patients' blood, depending on the form of chronic viral hepatitis, differ slightly.

The study found a decrease in IL-6 levels by 2.15 times in y patients of group 1 ($p < 0.05$), 1.6 times in y patients of group 2 ($p < 0.05$).

The results of studying IL-8 levels showed a tendency to increase in y patients of group 1 and a slight decrease in y patients of group 2 groups. The data obtained indicate the likelihood of bacterial and/or exacerbation of viral infection against the background of HCV.

As a result, a statistically significant decrease in MCP-1 was found to 262.1 ± 15.2 pkg/ml ($p < 0.05$) y large 1st group, to 255.8 ± 17.9 pkg/ml ($p < 0.05$) y large 2nd group, against the control values - 362.9 ± 25.3 pkg/ml.

The study of the interferon status of the patients selected for the study showed a statistically significant increase in the level of IFNa to 14.34 ± 0.65 pg/ml in patients of the 2nd group versus the control- 12.24 ± 0.64 pg/ml ($p < 0.05$). At the same time, the given interferon of y patients of group 1 was at the level of control values.

The analysis of IFN synthesis showed a significant increase in its effect in patients of both groups 1 and 2: up to 49.43 ± 3.73 pg/ml and 51.16 ± 3.48 pg/ml, respectively, against the control- 30.62 ± 2.62 pg/ml, $p < 0.05$. Consequently, an

increase in the synthesis of interferons shows the activation of the protective mechanisms of the body in CVD.

The study found a significant increase in TNF α levels in patients of group 2 by 1.58 times ($p < 0.05$).

The obtained result shows viremia and a higher risk of thrombosis in HCV.

Taking into account the pathogenetic mechanisms of the development of HCV, the level of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) in patients of this category was determined. At the same time, there was no significant increase in the level of VEGF in both study groups to 189.1 ± 24.9 pg/ml in y patients of group 1, to 231.2 ± 38.54 pg/ml in y patients of group 2, with respect to control indicators - 180.26 ± 35.9 pg/ml.

Conclusions

1. A decrease in IL-6 levels was found to be 2.15 times in y patients with chronic viral hepatitis C ($p < 0.05$), 1.6 times in y patients with chronic viral hepatitis B ($p < 0.05$).
2. A statistically significant decrease in MCP-1 was found in patients with chronic viral hepatitis.
3. An increase in the synthesis of IFN α in chronic viral hepatitis has been established, which shows the activation of the body's defense mechanisms in chronic viral hepatitis.
4. A significant increase in TNF α y levels in patients with chronic viral hepatitis B was found to be 1.58 times ($p < 0.05$), which confirms viremia and a high risk of thrombosis.

References:

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